

Indoor Air Quality Determination and Purification Using IOT, A Review

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Abstract—There are numerous health issues that indoor and outdoor air pollution is known to cause. Monitoring pertinent variables and locating pollutant sources are crucial for enhancing air quality. The design and development of a low-cost, mobile Internet of Things (IoT) Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) monitoring system with a approx 10-hour battery life are presented in this work. The device is designed for the monitoring of temperature, humidity, CO₂, PM₁₀, and total VOCs. This platform relies on an IoT and a cloud computing technology to monitor indoor air quality anywhere and anytime.. The device is composed of a microcontroller, pollutant detection sensors. And lastly for this project one of our main focuses is to make it portable and purification is done based on input received.

Keywords—Portable Air Purifier, Introduction of things, Indoor Air quality, CO₂, Potable.

carried out by gathering information from numerous remote-accessible sensors. This study was based on a number of earlier ones that had already been done. There have been studies in the past that have controlled and monitored the air quality in the space. This study is also based on our investigation into the design of remote communication for tracking air quality and offering a remedy by setting up a purification system. Several airborne substances, including O₃, SO₂, CO, and particulates, as well as temperature and humidity, will be measured by the system. Remote monitoring of the air quality will be done using websites and purification is done based on input received and the input is based on a certain value that we fixed as a threshold in our programming that we will get by using the web browser on the real time basis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Small solid and liquid particles suspended in the air are referred to as "fine particulate matter" (FPM). Compared to other air pollutants, they are the main cause of air pollution and have the biggest negative effects on individuals. Poor air quality can have negative effects on health and is bad for all living things. It's important to be aware of the air quality in a certain region in order to prevent things that could make health problems worse. As a result, it's important to regularly check the local air quality. Temperature, humidity, and air-contained chemicals including ozone, sulfur dioxide, carbon monoxide, and particles can all be measured as part of an air quality monitoring process. We can currently measure the proficiency level metrics to assess the state of the air quality thanks to advancements in sensor technology. IoT (Internet of Things) advancements have also aided remote monitoring technology. In this study, we develop an IoT-based monitoring system to continuously track the air quality in a specific location. Monitoring is

II. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

For the investigation, only studies that reference indoor air quality are chosen. Mapped studies on IAQ were gathered from the two databases. Studies on monitoring systems that were used to gauge the room's air quality as well as publications regarding IAQ using IoT as a method are comparable. The technology that can be utilized to monitor indoor air quality is the focus of the studies that were chosen. Articles in English that have been published during the last two years meet the eligibility requirements. Authors eliminated any articles that did not meet the qualifying requirements, and duplicate articles were not taken into consideration.

2.1 Identification and Data Processing

As a result, the study is chosen from all three databases, first by choosing titles and then by removing duplicate and unrelated papers. Choosing the abstract and carefully reading it to find relevance to the subject to encourage further, in-depth reading of the chosen work. The authors then compiled the publications that were most closely connected, synthesized the research, and processed it using EXCEL with the existing data.

3. LITERATURE SURVEY

3.1. Search Strategy

By selecting research information articles from two databases, a systematic search is conducted. The constructed query serves as the foundation for the database search. A few databases have background in engineering and science. IEEE Xplore exists.

Association for Computing Machinery's digital library (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>), Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com>), and Computerized Manufacturing (<https://dl.acm.org/>). On September 2, 2021, the search was conducted using the advanced search option.

A protocol describing the justification, hypothesis, and techniques of the intended review should be established for a systematic review. In addition, some assessments indicate if a new methodology may be applied and offer suggestions.

Digital Library	IEEE Xplore	Google Scholar
Language	English	English
Years	2019-2021	2019-2021
Type	Paper,Journal	Paper,Journal

Table 1: Search Strategy

[1].The paper describes the development of a portable air quality monitoring device considering the fine particulate matter(FPM,mixture of solid and liquid particles suspended in air) being harmful for the respiratory system and cardiovascular system. The study is further extended and applicable in humidity sensors also.

[2].This Study shows the development of a IOT Based Air quality monitoring system along with a an blynk application for user recommendations.The device is emphasized in measuring PM2.5 PM10,temperature,humidity and illuminance.The device is enabled with real time login system in hourly format or average time format.It has a 30 hour battery life.The total expenditure of the model is \$200.

[3].This Article is based on how to improve the sense of comfort. Determination of the parameters leading to improvement of sense of comfort.

[4] This paper proposes an Internet of Things (IoT) enabled system for monitoring and predicting PM2.5 concentration on both edge devices and the cloud.This paper propose and evaluated a hybrid NARX architecture hosting many

[5]The Web of Things (WoT) standards are the main topic of this essay's author's focus in order to provide interoperability to the IoT application layer. Depending on the underlying hardware and the application protocol chosen, the platform is based on a Web of Things capable ofexposing its own Thing Description with 15 to more than 2000 resources.

[6] In this paper many machine-learning methods are used for air pollution forecasting.Moreover, the authors compare hybrid deep-learning methods (convolutional neural network (CNN)—long short-term memory (LSTM) and CNN—gated recurrent unit (GRU)) with several stand-alone methods (LSTM, GRU) in terms of predicting PM concentrations in 39 stations in Seoul.

[7] This research describes a low-cost LoRa- based Internet of Things big data collection and analysis system for tracking indoor air quality.A gateway collects this data and sends it to a cloud-based LoRaWAN network, which broadcasts the information through MQTT.The sensor nodes' IAQ data is prepared using Cayenne LPP and sent over a LoRa transmitter.Charts and visualizations created by API integrations in the database are used to execute data analysis on the IoT big data that was collected.

[8] Traditional air quality monitoring stations need substantial infrastructure, skilled workers, and are both static and highly expensive.This study discusses a prototype personal air quality monitor that uses low-cost sensors, low-power IoT devices for communication, and cloud data storage. I also demonstrates how real-time data

monitoring can be accomplished from any device that supports a browser by merging IoT technologies. Monitoring pollution levels at the user's location and using this information to build a profile of the city or area to more precisely estimate dangers at the individual level was a crucial component.

[9] This paper describes the creation of a platform for IoT-based indoor air quality monitoring. The air quality measuring instrument utilized in the platform was subjected to tests to confirm its accuracy using a technique recommended by the Korean Ministry of Environment. We examined the device's desirable performance and indoor air quality monitoring accuracy.

[10] The system illustrated in this paper is based on the application of IOT Architecture On developing of a air quality determination device using various sensors for measuring the impurity parameters.The system can further be integrated with wifi module.This device can be installed in home and industries wherever the matter of air quality is concerned.The measure of good and bad is decided using the AQI around us

S.NO	AUTHOR	POLLUTANTS	SENSORS
1.	Marin Berov Marinov, Dimitar Iliev Iliev, Todor Stoy-nov Djamiykov,	Dust,volatile Organic Compound,Smoke and lastly most of the particles with diameter larger or equal to 0.3um.	Uses different type of air quality monitoring sensors,IR sensors
2.	Siavash Esfahani, Piers Rollins, Jan Peter Specht, Marina Cole	VOCs,CO2,PM2.2 And PM10.	The current prototype includes a sensor array,which contains major air pollutants,such as TVOCs And PM.
3.	Judit Maria Pinter,Marton L. Kiss	Gasses, Vapours,Dusts,Radioactive gasses	Temperature,Humidity Sensors etc.
4.	Ahmed Samy Moursi,Nawal EL-Fishawy	COx Compound,NOx Compound,Sulphur oxides SOx.	Different Kinds of sensors are used.
5.	Daniel Ibaseta,Julio Molleda,Fidel Diez,Juan Granda	Nitrogen Dioxide,Ozone,Sulphur Dioxide	A wireless sensor is used.
6.	Guang Yang 1,HwaMin Lee 2, and Giyeol Lee 3	PM10 and PM2.5	no sensors used , CNN RNN models used
7.	Matthew Meli,Edward Gatt,Owen Casha,Ivan Grech,Joseph Micalle	Temperature,Humidity,Pressure,Carbon Dioxide, VolatileOrganic Compounds,Particulate Matter	IOT sensor
8.	Sean Mc Grath, Colin Flanagan,Liaoyuan Zeng,Conor O’Leary	PM2.5,PM10,SO2,NO2,Lead,Carbon Monoxide,Ozone	Ozone SPEC Sensor (O3) Module - 968-046:,Carbon Monoxide SPEC Sensor (CO)
9.	JunHo Jo,ByungWan Jo ,JungHoon Kim , SungJun Kim,and WoonYong Han	concentration of aerosol, VOC, CO, CO2, and temperature-humidity	Microcontroller and a dust laser sensor. Organic Volatile Compound Sensor. a carbon monoxide detector. Sensor for Temp. and Humidity (DHT11)
10.	Rohan Kumar Jha	NO2,CO and PM2.5	Software and hardware for the Arduino UNO, as well as the gas sensors MQ135, MQ7, and dust sensor GP2Y1010AU

Table 2:Monitoring Air Quality Parameters and Pollutants

IV. DISCUSSION

This study's objective is to evaluate an indoor air quality (IAQ) monitoring system that uses an Internet of Things (IoT) approach on a campus area by conducting a thorough evaluation of previous research. The outcomes of the articles were divided into five categories in order to further examine the issue. The categories include IAQ monitoring system, IAQ on campus, IAQ data gathering, monitoring IAQ utilizing Internet of Things, and IAQ monitoring problems. This study classified a different study that included IAQ and only focused on literature. The information gathered was reviewed carefully and extensively from sources that were relevant to the subject area. This section will also cover the topic's difficulties and suggested solutions.

4.1 Indoor Air Quality Monitoring System

The majority of the publications cover the monitoring system for IAQ, and based on the survey, chosen articles from three databases were divided into four groups. Many scholars address monitoring systems from the publications that review studies, offer techniques, evaluate or compare, as well as construct systems. Also covered and evaluated are the various forms and gadgets for IAQ parameter monitoring. An existing review states that health issues including allergies and respiratory illnesses increase the significance of IAQ monitoring methods and data. The use of an Arduino microcontroller and inexpensive sensors was suggested as a way to conduct continuous monitoring at a minimal cost. Only studies that discuss indoor air quality were chosen for the research. The two mapped research on IAQ were combined. Publications about indoor air quality (IAQ) utilizing IoT as a technique and studies on monitoring systems that were used to measure the room's air quality are comparable. The chosen research concentrates on the technologies that can be used to assess indoor air quality. The criteria are met by English-language articles that have been published during the previous two years. Articles that did not satisfy the qualifications were excluded by the authors, and duplicate articles were not taken into account. To determine the effectiveness and performance of the sensors utilised in the monitoring system, evaluation and comparison with IAQ monitoring tools were also conducted. System development papers on IAQ are the most prevalent.

The several sensor types that were used in the experiment are listed in Table 2, along with a summary of the pollutant data that was collected. Summaries of the pollutants used by earlier researchers to develop a system for monitoring air quality are included in 24 studies pertaining to system development. system. Authors are aware that several types of sensors were also employed based on previous research.

The majority of sensors are used to track temperature and humidity.

V. DESIGN OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

Creating a schematic range is the initial step in system design. We employ four different types of sensors, namely MQ-7, MQ1-131, MQ-135, and PM10, to measure various sorts of particles in the air. Then use the Arduino IDE to

programme the Arduino Uno. An editor called Arduino IDE is used to create programmes for Arduino[20]. Create a channel in ThingSpeak so that you may collect the measurement data that the Arduino sends. By visiting the ThingSpeak API URL we acquired after creating a channel to receive data, we may transmit data from Arduino. Arduino uses the WIFI ESP8266 module to connect to the ThingSpeak API. The MQ-7 sensor is used to measure the CO compound concentrations in the atmosphere. The analogue sensor MQ-7 is used. The MQ7 gas sensor has the qualities of being stable, long-lasting, and very sensitive to CO. To measure carbon monoxide gas, this sensor employs a heater power source of 5V AC/DC and a circuit power supply of 5VDC, measuring distance of 20-2000 ppm. MQ-7 is attached to Arduino's A2 analogue pin . We utilize the MQ-131, an analogue sensor, to measure the air's ozone concentrations.. The microcontroller's VCC pin is coupled to a 5V (VCC) power source that powers the MQ-131. The sensor's output voltage will rise if it detects O3 gas in the air. so that a deoxidation process can take place and the gas concentration will drop. Calculating the difference between the sensor resistance value and sensor resistance in pure air yields the O3 gas concentration value.

Air. The purpose of the MQ-135 sensor, a gas sensor, is to measure the quality of the air in a space so that it can change from being a resistor to a semiconductor or voltage conductor. Other gases besides SO2 that can be measured with MQ-135 include ammonia, aromatics, benzene vapour. We use PM10 to monitor airborne particles in addition to various gas concentrations. Airborne particles smaller than 10 microns (micrometers) can be measured by a PM10 sensor. The Pm10 sensor is connected to an Arduino A3 analogue pin in the schematic of the circuit.

VI. METHODOLOGY

Along with two other sensors, the DHT11 and MQ135 sensors were used in this experiment. Unlike the MQ135, the DHT11 sensor monitors the air's temperature and humidity. The main contaminants that the sensor searches for are the levels of CO, CO2, and alcohol in the air. When conducting research, the research technique is an essential component, and via the deliberate approach. Because the researcher must follow the instructions of the technique, it is not appropriate to explain the problem and the study's objectives in isolation. The web was created using the waterfall approach, a systematic and sequential procedure. Prior to the system and software design, implementation, unit testing, system testing, integration (integration and integration), operation, and maintenance, it begins with the definition of the requirements (operational and maintenance). The DHT11 sensor is required for this investigation since it monitors temperature and humidity, whereas the MQ-135 sensor measures air contaminant levels. The Arduino Uno is connected to these two sensors. The Arduino Uno is then linked to the Raspberry Pi to serve

as a data container for Arduino Uno input. Data is sent to a web server using Wi-Fi as a wireless internet connection. The following data will then be shown by the web server:

1. Temperature
2. Air humidity
3. Air quality

The key data variables in the majority of research have been temperature and humidity, followed by concentrations of carbon dioxide (CO₂), volatile organic compounds (VOC), particulate matter (PM), and carbon monoxide (CO) (CO). Metrics for measuring air quality include contaminants (CO).

VII. OVERVIEW OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

Fig 1:Proposed flow diagram for research implementation

Our suggested system model aims to design and construct pollution monitoring that will be installed in a specific site and to expand concern web-oriented data that is ready to be made accessible to the general public. Figure 1 in the text above details the proposed system flow and planned flow of research implementation. We shall retrieve data from pertinent sensors in particular locations for our proposed system. The ESP8266 WiFi module will gather all the information from sensors and outside libraries. Data will be forwarded to distant databases after being collected. Through a web application, the data repositories will be connected to the user interface. Everyone can use this website application to get real-time updates on the pollution levels in the areas they care about. Data can be visualized using this online application in the form of reports or chart formats. so that the user can decide appropriately in accordance.

The purpose of the MQ-135 sensor, a gas sensor, is to measure the quality of the air in a space so that it can change from being a resistor to a semiconductor or voltage conductor. Other gases besides SO₂ that can be measured with MQ-135 include ammonia, aromatics, benzene vapour. We use PM10 to monitor airborne particles in addition to various gas concentrations. Airborne particles smaller than 10 microns (micrometers) can be measured by a PM10 sensor. The Pm10 sensor is connected to an Arduino A3 analogue pin in the schematic of the circuit. The key

differences between our proposed system and existing system is illustrated below.

EXISTING SYSTEM	PROPOSED SYSTEM
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Systems have not emphasized portability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Our System is portable and can be used anywhere.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adequate solution to fix the problem of impurities is not provided. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We have provided the solution as a purification of air by eliminating the pollutants in the area.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only a few have come up with the concern of Dust particles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Our system will monitor the dust particles as well
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Existing systems have provided the real time monitoring but extraction of data is not possible at later moment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cloud facility is included in the model for comparing the previous and current scenario of the air quality.

Table 3:Comparison of Existing and Proposed System

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this research, we offer an IoT-based air quality monitoring system that may use a website to display the monitoring data in real-time. The sensors utilized in this study include the DHT11, which measures temperature and humidity, and the MQ135, which measures CO and CO₂ levels. The website receives data from the sensors using Arduino and Raspberry Pie. To evaluate the capabilities of the suggested system, smoke containing CO was injected to the area around the sensors for testing purposes. The research's findings demonstrate that the website can accurately provide each parameter's level, the system can recognise an increasing CO level, and the website may display the real-time changes to the parameters and then offer suggestions based on the typical pollutant level. The temperature and humidity were both accurately sensed by the system. More sensors are supposedly required for future studies in order to identify more airborne particles. There is a demand for sensors that can identify PM10, PM2.5, O₃, NO₂, and other air contaminants. The employed sensors should be simple to implement and compatible with Arduino. In order to provide a better depiction of the air quality, more precise pollution level calculations should be investigated. With more auxiliary sensors and improved estimation of the air quality level, We think that this research will result in a system for measuring air quality that is more accurate, which will be very beneficial to human life.

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